

Development of Tai Chi Practice Application with Machine Learning Approach

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Abstract

Tai Chi is a traditional martial art that emphasizes slow, continuous movements, body alignment, balance, and coordinated force generation. Although Tai Chi is widely considered as a low-impact form of exercise, the accuracy of posture execution plays a critical role in ensuring both training effectiveness and physical safety. Repeated incorrect movements may lead to improper weight distribution and joint alignment, potentially resulting in long-term muscular tension or joint strain. This project develops a prototype application for detecting the correctness of Tai Chi postures, using the movement “Double Punch to the Ears” (DPE) as a case study. Correct movement demands proper timing and alignment of multiple joints. These make the movement challenging for beginners and difficult to self-correct without guidance, especially when training without an experienced instructor.

Much research has been conducted in this field, for examples [1, 2, 3]. Wang and Chen [1] developed a real-time Tai Chi training system using Kinect depth sensors and skeleton tracking algorithms, aiming to provide interactive feedback for general Tai Chi practice rather than detailed posture correctness evaluation. Lopez et al. [2] focused on the TAICHI algorithm for generating human-like Tai Chi arm movements for robotic manipulators, with the objective of motion imitation in robotics rather than human training. Aouaidjia et al. [3] employed vision-based 3D pose estimation to study Tai Chi learning from a human-factor perspective, emphasizing user perception and usability instead of automated correctness classification. In contrast to all of these existing research, our work targets the correctness evaluation of a single complex Tai Chi movement, DPE, using a lightweight vision-based approach and confidence score analysis, without requiring specialized sensing devices.

This application is designed to assist Tai Chi practitioners by automatically analyzing movement execution and providing real-time feedback. Motion data captured during practice is processed and compared with reference patterns that represent correct performance of DPE (see system overview in

Figure 1). ExpoGO is used to stream the data to the mobile application. The input video stream is processed frame by frame at 1 frame per second (fps). Human pose estimation is performed using MediaPipe, which extracts key body landmarks to calculate joint angles and segment lengths of the arms, legs, and body core [4]. These features are then structured and stored in a tabular format to form the dataset. The dataset is constructed from 100 videos, each with a duration of approximately one minute. Finally, the extracted features are used to train a machine learning model (Ensemble Learning algorithm built on decision trees) with XGBoost. The model is used for predict and analyze the human pose. The system evaluates whether the posture is performed correctly. A posture is defined as “correct” when the extracted pose features (e.g. joint positions and joint angles) fall within predefined acceptable threshold ranges (0.7-1.0) derived from reference poses. By delivering immediate feedback, the system helps practitioners recognize and correct errors as they occur, which can improve learning efficiency and reduce the likelihood of developing improper movement habits.

Figure 1: Overview of Development of Tai Chi Practice Application.

Currently, the system is capable of evaluating DPE only. Initial experimental results suggest that the overall system framework and posture recognition approach are viable. However, the accuracy of the system remains limited with 0.998 Mean Squared Error (MSE) of Confidence Scores, implying that the model may suffer from overfitting due to the small dataset size. This limitation could be addressed by increasing the number of training samples, indicating the need for further refinement. Due to insufficient data - small size of the training dataset (100 of 1-minute videos) - the model has limited exposure to variations in body structure, execution speed, movement amplitude, and individual practice styles. This lack of diversity reduces the system’s ability to generalize to new users and unseen movement patterns. Additionally, subtle differences between correct and near-correct executions of DPE present further challenges for accurate classification.

Future work aims to improve the accuracy and practicality of the proposed system. Large Language Models (LLMs) will be incorporated to generate concise and intuitive posture correction feedback. The system will extend to support more Tai Chi movements. The workflows and algorithms will be

optimized to enhance robustness and consistency. The system will also be evaluated with real users in practical training scenarios, and user feedback will be used to guide further refinement.

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